

NUMERICALLY PREDICTED DAMAGE AND FAILURE ENVELOPES OF COMPOSITES FEATURING NONLINEAR MATERIAL BEHAVIOR

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Keywords: *Progressive damage and failure, Textile composites, Finite Element analysis, Plane periodic unit cell*

Abstract

A simulation methodology is proposed which combines linear elastic analyses of large scale laminated composite structures and nonlinear unit cell predictions to account for local nonlinear material behavior at the ply level. In a two-step procedure nonlinear unit cell simulations are conducted first. The results can then be used to draw “energy dissipation envelopes” in stress and strain space and to perform post-processing on linear large scale structural analyses. Based on the concept of energy dissipation monitoring, the macroscopic material point exertion is assessed. The methodology is demonstrated using a generic nacelle structure built from laminated textile composites.

1 Introduction

Fiber reinforced polymers are increasingly used when designing high performance and lightweight structures. In this context, carbon/epoxy laminates comprising several layers of continuous unidirectional (UD) fibers and textile preregs, respectively, are especially important due to their exceptional mechanical properties. Such laminates

Fig. 1. Length scales of a composite laminate comprising textile layers.

offer high specific stiffness combined with high specific strength and provide the possibility of tailoring the composite properties as required by the prevailing loading of the structure. However, the intrinsic complexity of the microstructure and the accompanying anisotropic nature of continuous fiber reinforced materials lead to considerable difficulties when designing (textile) composite parts.

Dealing with laminated composites implies to distinguish between different length scales, Fig. 1. The scale of the fibers (microscale) represents one end of the considered scales. Here, the behavior of the fibers, the matrix, and the fiber/matrix interaction are considered. The other end of the considered length scales is defined by the size of the considered macro structure (macroscale) and involves the macroscopic loading and boundary conditions. Depending on the specific problem there might be one or more intermediate lengths scales often denoted as mesoscale. A typical example of such an intermediate length scale is the laminate scale, which incorporates the interaction of individual plies. Here, the classical lamination theory or layered shell formulations are commonly applied. In case of textile laminates a further intermediate length scale can be introduced accounting for the textile architecture. In the following, the term mesoscale will exclusively address this textile scale. Effects present at each of these length scales influence the performance of the laminate and, hence, have to be accounted for in some way.

In industry, a common approach to deal with laminated composites is using apparent or effective linear elastic properties of the plies or laminates (applying lamination theory) in combination with empirical or phenomenological based failure criteria. These criteria, generally termed as first ply failure (FPF) criteria, use the acting stresses and strains, respectively, see e.g. [1, 2], to reveal the loading state

which is supposed to induce the “first” failure at ply level. Implicitly, they assume linear elastic material behavior. They do not account for any material degradation and cannot give any information on what is happening after this first ply failure. Moreover, in real composite parts, occurrence of first ply failure does not necessarily lead to the ultimate failure of the whole structure, it merely initiates nonlinear mechanisms within the composite. Clearly, it would be of interest to obtain more information about the characteristics of the response beyond the elastic limit, i.e. the FPF, such as whether there is hardening or softening and whether or not there is some “strength reserve”.

This information may be gained by conducting detailed nonlinear simulations accounting for different damage and failure modes, like material degradation, plasticity, delamination, etc. In combination with numerical solution schemes, e.g. the Finite Element Method (FEM), moderately sized macroscale, nonlinear analyses can be performed (at least to some extent), which also account for stress redistribution due to the nonlinear material behavior. Even though this approach is widespread in academic and research institutions, see e.g. [3, 4], the accompanying computational demands prevent its applicability for large scale structures in industrial practice. This restriction is especially true if textile layers are present within the laminate as the complex microstructure requires highly refined meshes further heightening the computational requirements. In most cases detailed investigations of textile laminates are restricted to the nonlinear behavior at the mesoscale. Such problems can be tackled using numerical homogenization tools like unit cell approaches [5]. Recently, some research groups have been working on computational homogenization techniques bridging the lengths scales by concurrent nonlinear simulations of unit-cells and macroscale structures [6, 7]. However, these strategies are still restricted to research type problems due to their vast computational requirements.

The aim of the current paper is to combine detailed nonlinear predictions and simple linear elastic, large scale simulations, without direct coupling. This way the predictive capabilities of the linear elastic simulations can be extended. In this context a central question arises, namely, “what are appropriate quantities to assess the nonlinear effects of an anisotropic material?” A scalar quantity would be advantageous compared to the tensor valued stress and strain fields and their nonlinear evolution. The von Mises equivalent stress, commonly used with

isotropic materials, cannot be used due to the present anisotropy. Here, the dissipated energies associated with the individual nonlinear (but dissipative) mechanisms will be used. In the following the proposed methodology will be denoted as *energy dissipation monitoring concept*.

The approach will be demonstrated for a generic nacelle structure built from textile laminates. First, at mesolevel, the evolution of the damage and plasticity modes are computed for “all” possible effective loading states based on unit cell considerations of a single woven ply using the energy dissipation monitoring concept. The respective results are stored in a database and energy dissipation envelopes are computed. In a second step, this information is employed at the structural scale to assess a given loading situation.

2 Energy Dissipation Monitoring Concept

The failure surfaces of fiber reinforced composites found in the literature are typically based on FPF criteria. These criteria use the stresses and strains, respectively, of the acting loading state to compute a scalar value which is interpreted as some risk or load factor. As FPF criteria are based on linear elasticity, these scalar measures cannot be used directly to assess the current material state within the nonlinear regime. However, such criteria are commonly used within continuum damage mechanics to predict damage onset. The respective damage models provide information on the accompanying dissipated energy – an accumulated scalar quantity – readily available to assess the current loading state, see Fig. 2. The same ideas can be applied to evaluate the loading state with respect to nonlinear plastic response based on the dissipated energy accrued within the applied plasticity models. This allows for a distinct interpretation of the nonlinear mechanisms, e.g. damage, plasticity, but also delamination, and lays the

Fig. 2. Uniaxial stress-strain curves of systems featuring either damage (left) or plasticity (right) as the only source of nonlinearity. The dissipated energy densities are shaded as well as crosshatched and the corresponding recoverable strain energy density is hatched.

foundation for the proposed evaluation concept. The phenomena can be assessed individually and the sequence of their occurrence and the progression upon load increase results naturally. Moreover, energy quantities are straightforward to be extracted from FEM simulations.

The proposed technique is applied at the mesoscale (in the case of laminated textile composites) as this length scale predominantly defines the nonlinear response of such material systems. To this end, nonlinear Finite Element simulations of respective unit cells are conducted and the evolution of the dissipated energies is monitored. To use the obtained data at the macroscale, the evolution data of the whole space of possible macroscopic local stress and strain states has to be provided. This implies that no direct coupling between the macro- and mesoscale appears. Hence, a fair number of radial load paths (effective stress and strain paths, respectively) are simulated at the mesoscale. The distribution of these paths is such that the whole (plane) stress space is covered homogeneously with a sufficiently fine resolution. In subsequent steps, the results of such computations may be used to incorporate non-uniform distributions better suited for the current problem. Based on these distinguished load cases, for each macroscopic loading state (local stress or strain tensor) the associated mesoscopic energy dissipation can be computed by interpolation between the data points. To get a dimensionless measure the dissipated energies, W , are normalized using the current total energy of the system as

$$p_i(t) = \frac{W_i(t)}{W_{\text{tot}}(t)}, \quad i \in \{\text{pla, dam, ...}\} \quad (1)$$

with, t denoting the (pseudo) simulation time which is associated with the load magnitude. The index i indicates the considered damage or plasticity mode. The total energy, W_{tot} , is the sum of the dissipated energies associated with damage, W_{dam} and plasticity, W_{pla} , as well as the elastic strain energy. Note that “artificial” energy contributions associated with the numerical solution procedure, like energy dissipated by the viscous regularization technique, are not to be included in the total energy. Once any of the ratios defined by Eq. (1) becomes nonzero, onset of the particular mechanism is detected. As such onset resembles the application of a classical FPF criterion in terms of the damage mechanism and of a yield criterion in terms of plasticity theory, respectively. The “energy dissipation evolution data” with corresponding stress and strain states is stored in a database and can be used in two ways. First, “energy

dissipation envelopes” in stress space can be drawn corresponding to arbitrary dissipation energy levels, e.g. for the initiation of the individual mechanisms and for various relative energies. Meaningful values of the latter may be defined from simulations of selected load cases (and, preferably, accompanying experiments). This way, an overview is given over directional sensitivity, damage evolution gradient, “strength reserve”, sensitivity to overloads, etc.

Second, the data can be utilized in an automated way, for which the predicted stress from the FEM analysis at a certain location of the large structure is used as input. Checking all locations while applying the energy dissipation evolution data gives information on critical spots and activated nonlinear mechanisms as well as their evolution and progress.

Since some hundred nonlinear simulations are necessary to compute reasonable refined envelopes, an efficient modeling and simulation strategy is essential. However, once determined, they can be used for arbitrary large structures comprising the same textile ply. Of course, different material systems dictate different data sets. Interpolation between such different data sets may be reasonable to minimize the number of required precomputed material system.

In case of laminates with reasonable thin layers, the proposed approach featuring a three dimensional loading space (plane stress and strain space, respectively) is sufficiently accurate. This implies that occurring macroscopic bending and twisting loads are translated into respective layer-wise membrane normal and shear loads, cf. classical lamination theory. If thick layers are considered, i.e. high gradients in thickness direction might appear, the energy dissipation monitoring concept can be enriched to cope with mesoscopic bending and twisting. Internally, this leads to a six dimensional loading space and therefore, more mesoscopic nonlinear simulations are necessary to accurately capture the effective loading space.

For both types (thin and thick layers), single ply unit cells are sufficient for most cases. Nevertheless, whole-laminate unit cells can be used to include further damage modes like delamination between the individual layers. As bending and twisting might be important, a six dimensional approach is highly recommended for whole-laminate unit cells. Of course, such whole laminate approaches require substantially more computational demands and therefore, may be restricted to simple unit cell geometries.

2.1 Radial stress vs. radial strain loading

The proposed approach is based on the stipulation that the stress components increase proportionally within the unit cell – as well as at the considered location in the structure. In the linear regime this assumption holds true and for slightly nonlinear stress-strain responses it is approximated reasonably well. However, for pronounced nonlinear stress-strain behavior (which may set in at elevated loads) predictions maybe expected to suffer from inaccuracy. Moreover, stress redistribution would occur in the macroscale model which cannot be accounted for by the present approach – the macroscopic simulations remain of linear type. To improve the predictive capabilities in such cases, the methodology is equivalently carried out under radial stress and strain loading of the unit cell. The respective strain paths are computed using the previously defined stress paths and the initial elasticity tensor. For the linear elastic case this mapping is exact. Thus, stress and strain controlled simulations give the same result before the onset of nonlinear mechanisms in the unit cell. Beyond the elastic limit the response due to strain controlled loading will deviate from the stress controlled one. Since stresses, as well as their strain equivalents, are based on linear elastic considerations, one cannot tell which loading scenario is the more realistic case. However, they are expected to state some upper and lower estimates on the possible behavior. Additionally, mildly deviating responses indicate that the assumptions are met in an approximate way. To visualize these estimates a simple one dimensional example is used. Figure 3 shows a respective stress-strain curve and corresponding evolutions of the energy ratios. In this particular case (1D problem) the

Fig. 3. Sketch of a nonlinear stress-strain curve in a one dimensional example, and corresponding evolutions of the dissipated energy ratios. The triangle and cross indicate the energy ratio based on (radial) stress evaluation, the plus denotes the (radial) strain one. The circle corresponds to the equal energy strategy.

stress and strain controlled loading leads to exactly the same results (black solid line). The plot further shows the evolution of dissipated energies associated with damage (solid, cyan) and plasticity (dashed, cyan). The mapping of the linear macroscale results to the nonlinear mesoscopic ones follows the underlying loading strategies. Stress controlled load cases are evaluated at equal stress level (triangle and cross symbols) whereas strain controlled cases issue an equal strain assumption (plus symbol). As already stated the resulting energy ratios can be treated as some upper and lower estimates. A third mapping technique assumes equal total energy at both length scale (hatched and shaded areas). This result (circle) typically resides between the former two and can be treated as an additional predictor of the currently acting nonlinear state.

For locations identified as critical by the proposed approach and for which results appear doubtful, a sub-modeling technique could be applied.

3 Application example

To demonstrate the usage of the energy dissipation monitoring concept a nacelle structure built from a woven laminate will be used. The first step is to compute the energy dissipation evolution dataset for the applied ply. To this end, a unit cell is set up within the FEM framework as described in the following section. The second step will deal with the simulation of the macroscopic structure, i.e. the nacelle part and the application of the energy dissipation evolution data.

All FEM simulations are carried out using the commercial solver Abaqus Standard 6.12 (Dassault Systèmes Simulia Corp., Providence, RI, USA), a Matlab 2013a (The MathWorks, Inc., Natick, Massachusetts, United States) script and several accompanying Python scripts.

3.1 Composite: Twill weave

The material system under consideration is a 2/2 carbon/epoxy Twill weave. The investigated (incorporated) nonlinear mechanisms are damage of the tows and yielding of the unreinforced matrix pockets. Since the computation of energy dissipation envelopes requires multiple nonlinear (implicit) simulations an efficient modeling and simulation strategy should be aimed at. In the present study a shell element based unit cell approach is applied which has been shown to be highly efficient in terms of computational performance and in obtaining accurate results at the same time [8]. Within this approach, all constituents are modeled using shell

elements only. A single layer unit cell is issued to further speed up the computation.

Geometry and mesh. The geometry of the considered weave is chosen to feature tows with a rectangular cross section and a piecewise linear ondulation path. Figure 4 shows a sketch of the model weave including the dimensions (in mm).

The reference surfaces of the shell elements are meshed by 4-noded shell elements with linear interpolation functions featuring a typical element size of $1/14^{\text{th}}$ of the tow width. In thickness direction a Simpson scheme with five section points is used. The individual shell elements are tied appropriately, representing perfect interfaces, i.e. no delamination is permitted. At the unit cell lateral boundaries the nodes are coupled appropriately to achieve plane periodic boundary conditions [9]. This way, the unit cell represents a macroscopic infinite sheet of heterogeneous material with plane stress boundary conditions in thickness direction. A detailed description of the unit cell including the couplings and periodic boundary conditions can be found in [8].

Applied material models. Within the shell element based modeling strategy, the tows are treated as strips of unidirectional fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) featuring transversely isotropic elasto-brittle behavior. The applied FRP damage model is readily available in Abaqus/Standard v6.12 [10] and is based on a Hashin criterion to assess damage initiation [11] accompanied by linear strain softening for both fiber and matrix dominated phenomena. The elements of the unreinforced matrix pockets are equipped with an

Fig. 4. Cross section of the 2/2 Twill weave showing the piecewise linear ondulation path, rectangular tow cross sections (hatched), and matrix pockets (shaded) with dimensions in mm.

elastic-perfect plastic isotropic material featuring a Drucker-Prager type plasticity model. A circular shaped yield surface in the deviatoric plane and associated flow are assumed. Table 1 lists the material properties for the tows as well as matrix pockets. The tow data was chosen according to [12] and the matrix data was obtained from the supplier data sheet [13].

3.2 Macroscale structure: nacelle part

The considered macroscopic generic structure represents a part of some nacelle as might be present in an aircraft engine. Figure 5 shows an isometric view of the whole part. The applied laminate comprises 13 layers of a 2/2 carbon/epoxy Twill weave as defined in the previous section with a stacking sequence of $[0_3/45_2/0_3]_5$, see Fig. 6. Here, 0° (direction of the warp yarns) corresponds to the axial direction of the structure. For simplicity reasons a constant layup is used throughout the whole structure.

Due to the symmetry of the structure, loading as well as material, only a sixth of the whole part has to be simulated. The respective sector is meshed using quadratic shell elements with reduced integration and a layered shell formulation. In thickness direction 3 section points per layer are used. (Simpson scheme). The required effective material data for the individual layers is computed based on a unit cell characterization of the chosen material system.

Fig. 5. Isometric view of the macroscopic nacelle structure.

Tab. 1. Material data for the tows and matrix pockets of the carbon/epoxy weave (unit cell) [12, 13], values indicated by * are estimated by the author.

Tows (60% fiber volume fraction)					Matrix pockets	
E_1	$E_2 = E_3$	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	$G_{12} = G_{13}$	E_{Matrix}	ν_{Matrix}
146 GPa	9 GPa	0.34	0.61	4.27 GPa	3.52 GPa	0.37
R_{11}^t	R_{11}^c	R_{22}^t	R_{22}^c	R_{12}	σ_y^t	Friction angle*
2100 MPa	1407 MPa	82 MPa	249 MPa	110 MPa	81.4 MPa	Dilation angle*
						25°

Loading conditions. The macroscopic boundary conditions simulate an artificial load case of a variable pull pressure. The axial sides of the nacelle are constraint by neighboring parts and the rear part (tapered surface) is subjected to an axisymmetric pressure load featuring a cosine based distribution as sketched in Fig. 7. The average pull per mm circumference is assumed to be 45 MPa.

4 Results

First of all, two double layer versions of the unit cell, in-phase and out-of-phase stacked, are used to compute the effective linear elastic properties of the chosen material system. To this end six independent load cases are prescribed and the respective responses are taken to homogenize the weave. The influence of adjacent layers is represented by taking the average of in-phase and out-of-phase stacking results. These are commonly referred to as some sort of lower and upper estimate. Table 2 lists the resulting engineering constants to be used with the large scale simulations.

4.1 Energy Dissipation envelopes

Using the master node concept [14] the required (radial) loading states are applied to the unit cell. As an effective orthotropic material symmetry is

Tab. 2. Effective single ply material data of the 2/2 Twill weave (structural scale).

E_x	E_y	ν_{xy}	G_{xy}	G_{xz}	G_{yz}
47 GPa	47 GPa	0.1	29 GPa	46 GPa	46 GPa

Fig. 6. Composite layup of the nacelle part comprising 13 layers of Twill weave.

Fig. 7. Sketch of the applied boundary conditions on the nacelle structure.

expected, only one fourth of the investigated stress, and strain space, respectively, has to be simulated. In total 81 different plane stress states, and 81 strain states (linear elastic equivalent, see Sec. 2.1) are simulated. Using the strategy defined in Sec. 2 the evolution of the individual energy ratios is extracted for each radial load path and the resulting energy dissipation evolution data is stored appropriately.

Initiation surfaces, i.e. FPF and yield envelopes, for the textile layer can be directly obtained by evaluation of the energy dissipation evolution fields for a very low energy ratio. Figure 8 shows the respective surfaces for a ratio of 0.00001 in the plane stress space. These surfaces are based on the radial stress simulation data, however, as the FPF denote the elastic limit, the radial strain based surfaces coincide perfectly. Of course, this “identity” is only valid for the initiation surfaces. Such FPF surfaces can be directly used at macroscale simulations to assess the currently acting stress and strain state, respectively. Moreover, a visualization in the mesoscopic effective stress and strain space, respectively, helps to understand directional sensitivity of the considered meso-structure, see Fig. 8.

To obtain these failure surfaces, linear elastic simulations would have been sufficient, however, the main focus is laid on the nonlinear regime. To this end, additional surfaces of equal dissipated energy ratio can be evaluated to highlight the load factor sensitivity of the particular loading direction, i.e. what’s happening if the load is increased proportionally. Figure 9 gives the evolution of the energy dissipation envelopes with respect to ply damage for radial stress loading in the $\sigma_{xx} - \sigma_{yy}$ sub-space. It is clearly visible that upon damage initiation compressive stresses are much more severe in terms of damage progression than tensile stresses. Similar to this, Fig. 10 shows the energy dissipation envelopes with respect to matrix plasticity for different energy ratios based on radial stress loading.

Fig. 8. Stress envelopes of a 2/2 Twill weave showing damage (red) and yield (blue) initiation surfaces due to radial stress loading.

Again, the compressive loading regime can be considered as more critical with respect to load increase. Note that, due to the applied material models, plasticity only appears in the rather small areas of unreinforced matrix pockets. The fiber bundles – shown to possess plastic behavior [15] – are assumed to remain elastic throughout the whole simulation and therefore, the amount of dissipated plastic energy may be under-predicted here. To cope with this problem, more advanced ply material models have to be used, cf. [16].

4.2 Demonstrator example

To apply the proposed concept at the macroscale, a user subroutine capable of employing the previously defined data is implemented in Abaqus/Standard. With this tool, the energy dissipation envelopes can be used during post-processing like conventional FPF criteria indicating the reserve factor or safety factor with respect to the current loading step. Figure 11 shows a contour plot of the reserve factor against FPF (i.e. damage onset) of the nacelle sector subjected to the prescribed pull load. This plot identifies the inner surface at the axial quadrant of the slotted hole to be the most critical location in terms of ply damage. A similar evaluation giving the reserve factor with respect to yield initiation can be conducted as well. To evaluate the severity and sensitivity of a particular macroscopic, local loading state the information regarding the nonlinear evolution of the individual

damage and failure modes stored in the energy dissipation evolution database is used.

Figure 12 shows the predicted evolution of the dissipated energy ratio associated with ply damage for the critical location with respect to the load factor. The black solid line represents the response for a radial stress based loading, whereas the cyan solid line is linked with the corresponding radial strain based loading. The dashed lines denote the equal energy evaluation strategies. Additionally, the load factor leading to damage initiation (dam Init) is marked with a circle and the load factor associated with the first occurrence of a nonlinear mechanism (NL Init) is indicated with a cross. The latter is defined as the minimum of the initiation load factors associated with damage and plasticity. The good agreement of the two equal energy lines indicate that the structural response of the unit cell subjected to radial stress based loading strongly resembles the response of the corresponding radial strain based loading for the particular macroscopic local loading state. Figure 13 gives the same type of information for the dissipated energy ratios associated with matrix plasticity.

Following Fig. 12, the applied macroscopic loading state results in local stresses which are beyond the first ply failure of the textile composite. However, the amount of dissipated energy at load factor one and the rather moderate increase of the progression curve suggest, that the laminate might sustain further load increase. Until a load factor of two, the energy

Fig. 9. Energy dissipation envelope in the σ_{xx} - σ_{yy} sub-space indicating different levels (in percent) of dissipated energy ratios associated with ply damage (radial stress loading).

Fig. 10. Energy dissipation envelope in the σ_{xx} - σ_{yy} sub-space indicating different levels (in percent) of dissipated energy ratios associated with matrix plasticity (radial stress loading).

dissipated due to damage is below 4.5% and 2%, respectively. Note that the more critical state, the radial strain based curve (cyan line), only represents some upper estimate.

The development of dissipated energy associated with matrix plasticity (Fig. 13) reveals that the yield criteria has been met at about 50 percent of the particular loading conditions. The steady (non-sensitive) trend following this initiation clearly shows that the associated nonlinearity plays a negligible role until load factors beyond one. The rather sharp increase of the dissipated energy at elevated load factors suggests that despite the early initiation, this mechanism actually starts acting at higher loads. If the energy fractions are compared quantitatively with the ones attributed to tow damage, matrix pocket plasticity may be considered as less dominant for the acting loading state. Note again, the applied tow material model does not account for matrix plasticity, thus, the amount the respective dissipated energy might be under estimated here.

Fig. 11. Contour plot of the predicted reserve factor at the inner shell surface (corresponds to the critical location) against damage initiation of the nacelle sector.

Fig. 12. Predicted evolution of the dissipated energy ratios associated with ply damage due to radial stress, and strain loading, respectively, at the critical location ($\bar{\sigma}^T = [-13.1 \ 148.1 \ 1.3]$ MPa).

As the sensitivity of the critical loading state is not obvious for all locations, the question may rise if another structural location gets more critical during load increase. This can be answered by assessing the predicted macroscopic stress fields not only using the already proposed initiation surfaces, but using additional “post-initiation” surfaces associated with a certain amount of dissipated energy. The latter immediately indicates whether the critical point remains the same, or other locations have to be assessed as well. Of course, one has to be aware that nonlinear effects like stress redistribution, are not included in the macroscale simulations, hence the considerations should remain in a mild nonlinear regime.

5. Summary

A simulation methodology is proposed which combines nonlinear unit cell simulations accounting for local nonlinear material behavior at the ply level and linear elastic analyses of large composite structures. The evolution of dissipative mechanisms in plies is predicted by unit cells and the dissipated energies of the individual damage, plasticity and failure mechanisms are computed. The results can be used to draw “energy dissipation envelopes” and to perform post-processing on structural analyses. The methodology is demonstrated using an artificial nacelle structure comprising multiple textile layers. The utilization of these ideas for other materials with (complex) nonlinear behavior seems to be feasible and fairly straightforward.

Fig. 13. Predicted evolution of the dissipated energy ratios associated with matrix plasticity due to radial stress, and strain loading, respectively, at the critical location ($\bar{\sigma}^T = [-13.1 \ 148.1 \ 1.3]$ MPa).

Acknowledgement

The funding of the Polymer Competence Center Leoben GmbH (PCCL, Austria) within the framework of the COMET-K1-program of the Austrian Ministry of Traffic, Innovation, and Technology and the Austrian Ministry of Economics and Labor is gratefully acknowledged.

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